

IT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN EUROPE

On average between 2014 and 2021 it increased by 112.22% for Desi countries

The DESI Index calculates the ability of companies to use information technology to respect the environment. Data is available between 2014 and 2021 for DESI countries with the exception of the United Kingdom.

The ranking of DESI countries by value of the use of information technologies for environmental sustainability in 2021. Portugal is in first place for use of information technologies in companies for environmental sustainability with a value of 7.93, followed by Luxembourg with a value equal to 7.14 and from Finland with a value equal to 6.66 units. In the middle of the table there are Romania with an amount of 5.41 units, followed by Ireland with a value of 5.31 and Latvia with a value of 5.05 units. Belgium with a value of 3.65 units, France with a value of 3.50 and Denmark with a value of 3.40 units close the ranking. On average, the value of the use of information technologies for sustainability by companies in DESI countries in 2021 was equal to an amount of 5.34 units.

Ranking of DESI countries by value of the percentage change between 2014 and 2021. Denmark is in first place by percentage value of the ability of companies to use ICT technologies for environmental sustainability with a value equal to 176.44% equal to a amount of 2.17 units, followed by France with a value equal to 168.79% equal to an amount of 2.20 units and by Belgium with a value equal to 159.73% equal to an amount of 2.24 units. In the middle of the table there are Latvia with a value equal to 109.33% equal to an amount of 2.64 units, Ireland with a value equal to 104.42% equal to an amount of 2.71 units, and the Romania with a value of 102.56% equal to an amount of 2.74 units. Finland with a value equal to 86.71% equal to an amount of 3.10 units, Luxembourg with a value equal to 82.59% equal to an amount of 3.23 units and Portugal with a value equal to 77.12% equal to an amount of 3.45 units. On average, the value of the use of information technologies for environmental sustainability grew by an amount equal to 112.22% between 2014 and 2021.

Machine Learning and Predictions. A machine learning analysis is carried out below to predict the future value of the use of IT technologies for environmental sustainability. The algorithms have been optimized through the minimization of MAE, MSE, RMSE statistical errors and the maximization of R2. The learning rate for training the algorithms is equal to 80% of the dataset used. The following ranking of the algorithms is then presented:

- SGD with a payoff value of 4;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 9;
- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 13;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 17;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 18;
- kNN with a payoff value of 25;
- Tree and SVM with a payoff value of 29;
- Constant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

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Therefore, the best performing algorithm in predictive terms is the SGD. Through the application of the SGD algorithm it is possible to verify the following predictions for the countries, namely:

- Romania with a variation from 5.4178 up to 5.929 or equal to a variation of 0.5113 equal to an amount of 9.4365%;
- Denmark with an increase from an amount of 3.4075 up to a value of 3.409 or equal to a change of 0.0016 equal to an amount of 0.0472%;
- France with a decrease from an amount of 3.5092 up to a value of 3.509 or a change equal to an amount of -0.004 units equal to a value of -0.0117%;
- Germany with a change from an amount of 3.8371 up to a value of 3.834 or a change equal to an amount of -0.0034 units equal to an amount of -0.0981%;
- Estonia with a variation from an amount of 4.6032 up to a value of 4.597 units or equal to a variation of -0.0063 units, equal to -0.136%;
- Belgium with a variation from an amount of 3.652 units up to a value of 3.647 units or equal to a variation of -0.0055 units equal to an amount of -0.1517%;
- Poland with a variation from an amount of 4.2376 up to a value of 4.231 or equal to a variation of an amount of -0.0069 units equal to a variation of -0.1638%; +
- Italy with a decrease from an amount of 4.322 units up to a value of 4.319 units or a variation of -0.0074 units equal to a value of -0.1706%;
- the Netherlands with a variation from an amount of 4,798 units up to a value of 4,789 units or equal to a variation of -0.0094 units equal to a value of -0.1949%;
- Latvia with a variation from an amount of 5.0568 units up to a value of 5.046 units or equal to a variation of -0.0109 units equal to an amount of -0.2165%;
- Czech Republic with a variation from an amount of 3.6829 units up to a value of 3.675 units or equal to a variation of -0.0081 units equal to an amount of -0.221%;
- Cyprus with a variation from an amount of 4.9091 up to a value of 4.897 units or equal to a variation of -0.0124 units equal to a variation of -0.2528%;
- Croatia with a variation from an amount of 6.4212 up to a value of 6.404 units or equal to a variation of -0.0178 units equal to a variation of -0.2769%;
- Hungary with a variation from an amount of 5.0201 units up to a value of 5.006 units equal to a variation of -0.0141 units equal to an amount of -0.2801%;
- Slovakia with a change from an amount of 6.5853 up to a value of 6.566 units or equal to a change of -0.0195 units or equal to an amount of -0.2954%;
- Ireland with a change from an amount of 5.311 units up to a value of 5.29 units or a reduction of -0.0159 units equal to an amount of -0.2984%;
- Bulgaria with a variation from an amount of 5.4184 up to a value of 5.402 units or equal to a variation of -0.0164 units equal to -0.3021%;
- Spain with a change from an amount of 6.5804 units up to a value of 6.559 units or equal to an amount of -0.0212 units equal to an amount of -0.3223%;
- Sweden with a variation from an amount of 6.2043 units up to a value of 6.183 units or equal to a variation of -0.021 units equal to an amount of -0.3388%;
- Finland with a variation from an amount of 6.6679 units up to a value of 6.645 units or equal to a variation of -0.0234 units equal to an amount of -0.3508%;
- Slovenia with a change from an amount of 6.3194 up to a value of 6.295 or a change equal to an amount of -0.0241 units equal to an amount of -0.3822%;
- Malta with a variation from an amount of 6.3703 units up to a value of 6.345 units or equal to a variation of -0.0258 units equal to an amount of -0.4055%;

- Lithuania with a variation from an amount of 6.3138 up to a value of 6.288 or a variation equal to an amount of -0.0256 units equal to an amount of -0.4063%;
- Portugal with a change from an amount of 7.9333 units up to a value of 7.9 units or equal to a change of an amount equal to -0.0336 units equal to -0.4396%;
- Austria with a change from an amount of 5.6576 units up to a value of 6.533 units or equal to a change of -0.0249 units equal to an amount of -0.4396%;
- Luxembourg with a decrease from an amount of 7.1429 units up to a value of 7.11 units or equal to an amount of -0.0334 units equal to an amount of -0.4677%;
- Greece with a variation from an amount of 5.0208 units up to a value of 4.729 units or equal to a variation of -0.2915 units equal to a variation of -5.8055%.

Conclusions. As is evident from the analysis carried out, companies find it difficult to use IT technologies in the sense of creating environmental sustainability. There is therefore no clear signal of connection between the tech world and the green world, and this could reduce the chances of success in the fight against pollution and climate change. Furthermore, it must be considered that information technologies tend to be energy-intensive and have a negative impact in terms of CO2 production.

Declarations

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References

- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Broadband Penetration in Europe. Available at SSRN 3953683.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe, *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.
- Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2021). Human Resources in Europe. Estimation, Clusterization, Machine Learning and Prediction. (September 29, 2021). *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The Finance-Innovation Nexus in Europe. *IJSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Human Resources in European Countries During the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(9), 145-171.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The SMEs Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Friendly Environment in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. Available at SSRN 4034298.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956853.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Giardinelli, V., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Cannone, F. (2022). Original Data Vs High Performance Augmented Data for ANN Prediction of Glycemic Status in Diabetes Patients. Available at SSRN 4082839.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Intellectual Assets in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Determinants of Internet User Skills in Europe. Available at SSRN 4113155.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.

Galiano, A., Leogrande, A., Massari, S. F., & Massaro, A. (2019). I processi automatici di decisione: profili critici sui modelli di analisi e impatti nella relazione con i diritti individuali. *Rivista italiana di informatica e diritto*, 1(2), 41-61.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe (No. 112619). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Workers in the Knowledge Economy in Europe (No. 112538). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment Impact of Innovation in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Prediction of Diabetes. Available at SSRN 4135264.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Broadband Price Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4036690.

Galiano, A., Leogrande, A., Massari, S. F., & Massaro, A. (2020). I dati non personali: la natura e il valore. *Rivista italiana di informatica e diritto*, 2(1), 61-77.

Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Fuzzy c-Means Clusterization and ANN-MLP Prediction of Malign Breast Cancer in a Cohort of Patients. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). The Role of Broadband Price Index in Fostering Economic Growth and Digitization in Europe. *Journal of Human, Earth, and Future*, 3(1), 32-54.

Massaro, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Text Mining Approaches Oriented on Customer Care Efficiency. Available at SSRN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Determinants of Lifelong Learning in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). International Scientific Co-Publications in Europe. Available at SSRN 4117970.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Giardinelli, V., & Massaro, A. (2022). ICT Specialists in Europe. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). e-Government in Europe. A Machine Learning Approach. (February 25, 2022).

Massaro, A., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Magaletti, N. (2022). Predictive Maintenance and Engineered Processes in Mechatronic Industry: An Italian Case Study. *International Journal*, (1), 37-54.

Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., Leogrande, A., & Massaro, A. (2022). Process Engineering and AI Sales Prediction: The Case Study of an Italian Small Textile Company. Available at SSRN 4026183.

Leogrande, A. (2021). The Destruction of Price-Representativeness. Available at SSRN 3994021.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). SMEs SELLING ONLINE IN EUROPE. *International Web Post*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7017850>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Electronic Invoices in Europe. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7021412>